

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	%Metal		%Sulfur		%Nitrogen		Δm mhos cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.				
MnL ₂ Cl ₂	14.95	15.008	15.39	17.51	7.52	7.68	8.5	5.90	1200	3300
MnL ₂ (SCN) ₂	13.16	13.35	30.81	31.17	13.58	13.61	12.0	5.85	1190	3150
CoL ₂ Cl ₂	15.36	15.50	16.59	16.87	7.16	7.36	10.5	4.8	1195	3200
CoL ₂ (SCN) ₂	13.98	14.19	30.57	30.88	13.24	13.48	10.00	4.9	1190	3200
NiL ₂ Cl ₂	15.74	15.87	17.16	17.30	7.46	7.57	7.5	—	1200	3300
NiL ₂ (SCN) ₂	13.96	14.14	30.72	30.84	13.35	13.49	8.0	—	1195	3100
CuL ₂ Cl ₂	16.72	16.99	16.90	17.12	7.25	7.49	10.5	1.79	1200	3150
CuL ₂ (SCN) ₂	15.08	15.13	30.23	30.49	13.16	13.34	12.5	1.78	1150	3200
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	17.28	17.36	16.80	16.99	7.35	7.43	10.0	—	1195	3250
ZnL ₂ (SCN) ₂	15.37	15.50	30.16	30.35	12.07	12.28	11.0	—	1190	3300
CdL ₂ Cl ₂	26.37	26.53	14.94	15.11	6.50	6.61	8.5	—	1190	3150
CdL ₂ (SCN) ₂	23.72	23.98	27.16	27.31	11.83	11.94	12.5	—	1195	3100
HgL ₂ Cl ₂	39.05	39.21	12.32	12.50	5.38	5.47	10.5	—	1200	3250
HgL ₂ (SCN) ₂	35.87	36.03	22.54	22.98	11.25	11.49	8.0	—	1190	3300

L=dithioamide.

band is not noticed. Magnetic moment values of 4.8 B.M. indicate a possible octahedral or distorted-octahedral configuration for these complexes.

Nickel(II) complexes show one absorption band ~ 500 (54) nm region typical of planar complexes. Diamagnetic nature of the complex from magnetic measurement supports the planar configuration.

One broad absorption band is observed in case of copper(II) complexes ~ 550 (3) nm region indicating a tetragonally distorted-octahedral stereochemistry. Magnetic moment values are ~ 1.79 B.M.

From the analysis, conductance and IR spectral data, zinc, cadmium and mercury(II) complexes have presumably an octahedral environment around the metal ions.

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Fluoroindates of Some Bivalent Metals

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MANY papers have been published on the fluoro compounds of indium¹⁻⁴. In view of the large number of fluoro complexes known for related elements, aluminium and gallium, it is reasonable to expect similar fluoroindates. Since the electronegativity for indium is 1.3, the In-F bond may be expected to be about 90% ionic⁵, and the radius ratio gives a maximum coordination number of eight for indium towards fluorine. Such highly coordinated complex should be stabilised by the triple charge on indium ion but mutual repulsion between adjacent fluorine atoms could decrease the maximum coordination number. That's why many hexafluoro indium compounds having the composition M^IM^{II}InF₆ are known^{6,7} whereas the only known pentafluoro compound⁸ containing bivalent metal is CoInF₅·7H₂O. The present work deals with the isolation and study of a number of pentafluoroindates of some other bivalent metals.

Preparation of fluoroindates: InF₃·3H₂O was prepared by evaporating the solution of freshly precipitated In(OH)₃ in dilute HF. InF₃·3H₂O (1 gm) was dissolved in water slightly acidified with dilute HF. A solution of the desired bivalent metal carbonate in very dilute HF was added to the first solution with constant stirring. The mixture was then evaporated on a water-bath to crystallisation. The crystals were filtered and recrystallised from their aqueous solutions faintly acidified with dilute HF. The crystals were filtered, washed with a little water and dried in air.

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND IR DATA OF SOME DIVALENT FLUOROINDATES

Compounds	Found(%)			Calc (%)			In-F(cm^{-1})
	M	In	F	M	In	F	
CuInF ₅ ·5H ₂ O	17.45	32.03	25.50	17.49	31.60	26.14	470(s)
CuInF ₅	23.15	42.15	34.60	23.24	42.01	34.75	—
NiInF ₅ ·5H ₂ O	16.40	32.13	26.77	16.37	32.03	26.50	430(s), 460(s)
NiInF ₅	21.88	42.62	35.48	21.86	42.77	35.38	—
CdInF ₅ ·6H ₂ O	26.00	26.42	21.83	26.13	26.69	22.08	470(s)
CdInF ₅ ·H ₂ O	33.08	33.65	28.02	33.04	37.75	27.92	—
CdInF ₅	34.68	35.50	29.32	34.88	35.63	29.47	—
ZnInF ₅ ·5H ₂ O	17.80	30.97	26.20	17.91	31.45	26.01	480(s)
ZnInF ₅ ·H ₂ O	22.20	39.00	32.48	22.29	39.15	32.40	—
ZnInF ₅	23.80	41.58	34.60	23.75	41.73	34.52	—
MnInF ₅ ·5H ₂ O	15.18	32.40	26.85	15.47	32.37	26.78	470(s)
MnInF ₅ ·H ₂ O	19.30	40.68	33.40	19.42	40.61	33.60	—
MnInF ₅	20.60	43.45	35.75	20.74	43.38	35.89	—

(s=sharp).

During the preparation if the HF concentration is maintained, high indium trifluoride gets precipitated along with the compound. These compounds hydrolyse in water and are insoluble in common organic solvents.

For analysing a compound it was fused with sodium carbonate and the fused mass was extracted with water. From the extract leadchlorofluoride was precipitated and the fluorine content determined argentometrically. Indium was separated⁹ from the other metals by double precipitation of indium as its hydroxide by adding ammonia in presence of ammonium nitrate. The divalent metals were estimated through their standard methods. The analytical results are reported in Table 1.

The fluoroindates were studied thermogravimetrically using a manually operated thermobalance at a heating rate of 4°/minute. All the compounds decompose below 100°. The pyrolysis curves of CuInF₅·5H₂O and NiInF₅·5H₂O show horizontal portions at 200-220° and 180°-200° respectively corresponding to the loss of 5H₂O, whereas the pyrolysis curves of the other fluoroindates show two horizontal portions at different temperatures indicating the stepwise loss of water molecules. The compound CdInF₅·6H₂O loses 5H₂O at 100° and further H₂O at 210°. ZnInF₅·5H₂O and MnInF₅·5H₂O lose 4H₂O at 110° and 160° respectively. The last water molecule is eliminated at 230° and 260° respectively. All about 400° the compounds decompose to yield a mixture of metal fluoride and oxide. The isothermal heating of the compounds at above mentioned temperatures yielded the less hydrated and anhydrous products. The analytical results of these are also given in Table 1. These results suggest that the water molecules present in the compounds are not identically bounded.

The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded in a Perkin Elmer apparatus on KBr pellets in the

region 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The IR spectra of the fluoroindates show sharp bands in the region 430-470 cm^{-1} due to In-F stretching frequencies¹⁰. The absorption bands at about 1610-1640 cm^{-1} and 3400 cm^{-1} due to the deformation and stretching vibrations of H₂O molecules are also observed which confirm the presence of water of crystallisation in these compounds. The bands due to In-F stretching frequencies for the different compounds are reported in Table 1.

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